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QUESTIONNAIRE

Date 10th June 2025

Unit name	University of Ljubljana
Country	Slovenia
Number of researchers	4 722 (Business report for the year 2024)
Number of students	37 472
Link to the website	www.uni-lj.si
Characteristics of research activities (max. 300 words)	The University of Ljubljana is a research-intensive and excellent arts university, striving for excellence and international recognition in all areas of its activities. In the field of research, UL covers and develops all areas according to the FRASCATI classification. The university brings together 23 faculties and 3 academies that cover the areas of arts, nature, technology, social sciences, humanities, medicine, health sciences, and sport.

Does your institution have a formal system for assessing researchers?

Yes **No**

If so:

	What document (Rector's ordinance, Senate resolution, national regulations) regulates the researchers assessment system?
1.	Criteria for Appointment to the titles of University Teachers, Researchers and Associates at the University of Ljubljana, adopted by the Senate of the University of Ljubljana, valid from Nov 2022 Appointment to the titles University of Ljubljana https://www.uni-lj.si/assets/Pravni-akti/Habilitacije/Trenutno-veljavni-akti-UL/Merila-za-volitve-v-nazive/Priloge-3-k-Merilom/Navodila-za-izvajanje-Meril-od-17.12.2024-cistopisUPB4-ENG.pdf
	What time frame of work is taken into account in the assessment?
2.	At the university, teaching and research roles are distinct but interconnected. University teachers are primarily responsible for teaching, while research is an integral part of their duties. Researchers may be appointed to university teaching titles (assistant professor, associate professor, professor) if they meet both qualitative and

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quantitative teaching competence criteria. Such teaching appointments are valid only as long as the underlying research title is valid.

Senior research fellows and senior research associates may also be appointed directly to the title of assistant professor if they meet the teaching competence requirements. For reappointment or promotion to a higher teaching title, prior application dates for research titles are considered.

Appointment durations vary: professors and senior research fellows receive indefinite appointments by the University Senate. Other roles—such as assistant and associate professors, and most research and teaching roles—are appointed by the faculty senate for fixed terms (3 to 5 years), with the possibility of reappointment under set conditions. Titles follow a defined sequence for both university teachers and researchers. Candidates seeking to extend their current title during a reappointment process must apply at least six months before the title's expiration.

What are the basic assessment criteria?

In summary, assessment is structured around:

1. Formal completeness of the application;
2. Meeting quantitative thresholds (research output, authorships, teaching, projects);
3. Qualitative evaluation of contributions in research, education, and professional impact;
4. A transparent review process with external oversight and clear decision language.

Detailed:

1. Formal Completeness & Documentation
 - Application completeness: Must include a signed request, curriculum details, teaching competence proof (if required), full bibliography/points tally, attachments (e.g. diplomas, evidence of foreign language), and digital signature.
 - Bibliography & points: Based on SICRIS/Cobiss data or manually compiled; must be accurate, with adjustments for accepted-but-unpublished works, guest research/teaching abroad, mentorship, etc.
3. Supporting evidence: Documentation for all claimed achievements—publications, projects, teaching evaluations, foreign experience, language proficiency, leadership roles, etc.
2. Quantitative (“Minimum Conditions”)
 - Research output: Meets minimum publication quantity and point-score thresholds per title (assistant/associate/professor).
 - First/lead authorship: Required number of first or lead-author works in recent appraisal period.
 - Other output: For teaching titles, a specified number of textbooks, teaching points, mentorships, student awards, etc.
 - Projects: Leadership of at least one project (research, development, or arts for relevant fields).
 - Foreign experience: Minimum duration of guest teaching/research abroad (≥ 30 days), with point allocation.
3. Qualitative Assessment
 - Research/Artistic Merit:
 - Independent research ability and problem-solving.
 - International recognition: number of citations, prestige of venue/publisher, awards, etc.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ National-cultural impact (where applicable). ○ Detailed analysis of key works—minimum 2 (assistant prof), 4 (associate prof), or 6 (professor). ● Teaching Quality (for pedagogical titles): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Descriptive evaluation—based on trial lectures, mentoring, course materials, and possible student feedback. ● Professional Impact: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Projects, patents, conference papers, and involvement in professional bodies. ○ Knowledge transfer, commercial or public outreach. <p>4. Review Process & Decision-Making</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reviewer Qualifications: At least three experts; must hold equal or higher academic rank; include at least one external reviewer. ● Conflict of Interest: Must be checked and disclosed. ● Review Structure: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Intro and verification of bibliography & points. 2. Check of minimum qualitative and quantitative conditions. 3. Analytical evaluation of academic/artistic work. 4. Teaching effectiveness (if applicable). 5. Assessment of professional contributions. 6. Clear conclusion on suitability. ● Institutional Oversight: Faculty verifies completeness, collects reviews (including student feedback), and forwards the file. Appeals are allowed for negative opinions.
4.	<p>Do the criteria or their importance differ for job groups (assistant/assistant professor/professor) and/or scientific disciplines?</p> <p>Yes, as explained in point 3.</p>
5.	<p>How are researchers informed about the assessment system and rules?</p> <p>Criteria are posted on UL internet side, both in Slovene and English. Procedure on gaining new habilitation title starts at member faculty level. Each pedagogical or research employee has his/her supervisor who guides him/her for his/her development. Habilitation committee of University of Ljubljana is second level university's organ that solves the applications approved by members' senates for specific / highest habilitation titles only - as defined in Statute of University of Ljubljana.</p>
6.	<p>Do scientists have an influence on determining the principles of assessment?</p> <p>Researchers have influence through various committees.</p>
7.	<p>Do they receive feedback after the assessment (in what form – written/oral)?</p> <p>Researcher's applications for the habilitation are lead formally as explained above and each researcher gets positive or negative decision, which is explained in specifics. This is valid also for pedagogic staff (as they are at the same time also partly researchers).</p>
8.	<p>Do you use electronic tools to assess scientific achievements?</p> <p>Development of electronic / digital tool is in the process. Currenty UL has pilot in work. Once pilot will be finished (expected by end of Jun 2025), all member faculties will launch new digital tool for habilitation process.</p>

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	Are there any automated elements in the assessment system, e.g. is there a possibility to generate achievements report from the employee portal?
	<p>SICRIS as Slovene national Research Information System – is national governed platform and serves for the Evaluation of bibliographic indicators of research performance, bibliographic indicators of performance for the appointment to title, citations. COBISS.SI - Authors / Researchers</p> <p>Researchers use this platform to extract the reports for their publications, citations – which is evaluated within the process of habilitation. Below is the summary of different habilitation titles and the process of obtaining them – as they relate to the question.</p> <p>As already mentioned above, UL has two levels of decision making (Faculty level Senate, UL level: Habilitation Committee and UL Senate):</p> <p>1. First level - faculty member, decides on following habilitation titles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -teaching assistant, - librarian, - specialist consultant, - senior specialist adviser, - specialist adviser - skills instructor. <p>9. The title of a research associate is junior researcher.</p> <p>2. Second level – Habilitation Committee of University of Ljubljana:</p> <p>I. Senate of Faculty finishes the process of habilitation and decides for following hab titles, after this is approved by HK UL:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Titles for university teachers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o associate professor, o assistant professor, o senior instructor, o instructor, o lector. • Titles for researchers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o senior research associate, o research associate. <p>II. UL Senate is authorized for the decision of the highest two habilitation hab titles, after this is approved by HK UL:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Titles for university teachers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o professor. • Titles for researchers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o senior.
10.	Does the assessment of scientific achievements consider bibliometric indicators??
	Yes, impact factor.
11.	Do the assessment criteria consider elements considered as Open Science?
	No.

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	How often is the assessment system changed or modified and for what reason (legislative changes or under the influence of opinions?)
12.	From 2012 to 2022 changes of the Criteria were formally changed almost every year. From 2022 till now there will be one formal change (which is in process) – include new national criteria of NAKVIS (national agency for accreditation of HE Institutions), include higher qualitative vs quantitative criteria, the UL affiliation, the recommendations from faculties, etc.
	Is the result of the assessment associated with a promotion, contract extension or other element, such as a salary increase?
13.	Each change of habilitation title to higher level, automatically changes their Position title and also their salary level. This automatism is valid only for Professors and Researchers.
	Are the criteria for scientific assessment related to the implementation of the university's strategy/vision/mission?
14.	Yes, fully relates to UL strategy, vision and mission.
	Are the most prestigious ERC grants particularly recognized and promoted in the assessment of scientific activity?
15.	No.